

New Butterflies and Microlepidoptera observations and notes in Baranya County, South Hungary, (1) (Lepidoptera)

Imre Fazekas

Abstract. Since the 1970s, the author has conducted a series of studies on the Lepidoptera fauna of southern Hungary (Baranya County), documenting more than 2,000 species. Among these are numerous taxa represented by single specimens or previously known only from historical literature records. In the present contribution, new and significant faunistic observations are provided, and the status of several species with formerly uncertain occurrence is critically reassessed. The study area represents the southernmost biogeographic region of Hungary, where ecological conditions and zoogeographic influences from the Balkan faunal region are most pronounced. The following species were examined: *Cochylidia moguntiana* (Rössler, 1864); *Dirhinosia cervinella* (Eversmann, 1844); *Ecpyrrhorrhoe diffusalis* (Guenée, 1854); *Polyommatus amandus* (Schneider, 1792); *Triodia amasinus* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1852); *Whittleia undulella* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1837).

Keywords. Lepidoptera, Hungary, Baranya County, faunistics, species distribution, rare taxa, biogeography

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Introduction

Baranya County constitutes the southernmost administrative region of Hungary, bounded by the Danube River to the east and the Drava River to the south. The predominantly lowland topography is punctuated by two distinct limestone orographic units: the Mecsek Mountains (max. 682 m a.s.l.) and the Villány Mountains (max. 442 m a.s.l.). Due to its proximity to the Mediterranean Basin, the region exhibits pronounced sub-Mediterranean climatic influences. Consequently, the local biota incorporates a high proportion of Mediterranean elements, a biogeographical characteristic that is exceptional within the Pannonian context (Fig. 1).

A comprehensive description of the Villány Mountains is essential for understanding the specific habitats of these species. Stretching from east to west, this mountain range functions as a veritable “ecological island” from both botanical and entomological perspectives; it is frequently referred to as the “Hungarian Dalmatia.” The northern slopes of the Villány Mountains are predominantly covered by mesophilous forest communities, including gorge forests, hornbeam–oak forests, scree slope forests, and summit forests. Furthermore, near the ridgeline—particularly on north-facing slopes–grassland communities such as *Festuco rupicolae–Arrhenatheretum* represent characteristic elements of the landscape.

In contrast, the southern slopes exhibit a heterogeneous mosaic of xeric forest types — most notably karst scrub forests and calcareous oak forests — interspersed with various grassland formations, including rocky grasslands and slope steppe meadows. In areas where the original vegetation has not been preserved in a near-natural state, secondary land use has significantly altered the environment. On the northern slopes, formerly dominated by hornbeam–oak forests, plantations of black locust (*Robinia pseudoacacia*) and various pine species are now widespread. Meanwhile, the southern foothill zones are extensively occupied by viticulture.

Fig. 1. The geographical location of Baranya County without the exact boundaries marked: M = Mecsek Mountains, V = Villány Mountains

Furthermore, the region holds significant importance for reconstructing the faunal history of the Carpathian Basin. Zoological investigations have been ongoing in this area since 1970 (Fazekas 2002). This paper presents selected faunistic records accumulated over the past 25 years, focusing on species of particular biogeographical and conservation relevance.

Habitat vegetation is characterised in detail because plant community structure is a key determinant of lepidopteran population persistence and distribution dynamics. Specific vegetation types function as "stepping stones" within a given biogeographic or ecological matrix, facilitating species colonisation and dispersal. It is argued that geographic toponyms alone are insufficient for documenting species occurrences; rather, occurrence data must be integrated with the vegetation classifications defined in the General National Habitat Classification System (Bölöni et al. 2011; ÁNÉR 2011).

Materials and Methods. This paper is based on the author's decades of field observations and collections, as well as data from the literature and museums. It interprets the occurrence of species within a vegetation and habitat typology framework, emphasising the role of "ecological stepping stones" in the survival and genetic connectivity of populations (Fazekas, 2026).

Faunistic Accounts

Hepialidae

Triodia amasinus (Herrich-Schäffer, [1851] (figs 2-3)

Hepialus amasinus Herrich-Schäffer, [1851]

According to Gyulai et al. (1974), *Korscheltellus (Hepialus) amasinus pinkeri* Daniel was recorded on Mount Szársomlyó in the Villány Mountains on September 26, 1969, based on a copulating pair (♂♀) collected by Z. Varga. This record represents the northernmost known occurrence of the species, which was originally described from Asia Minor and subsequently re-

Fig. 3. The hypothetical dispersal pattern of *Triodia amasinus* from the Balkan refugia toward the southern regions of the Carpathian-Pannonian Basin

ported from the Balkan Peninsula (e.g., former Yugoslavia, North Macedonia). The population inhabiting the xerothermic southern slopes of Mount Szársomlyó — an area supporting numerous relict southern plant and insect taxa (e.g., *Festuca dalmatica*, *Trigonella gladiata*, *Medicago orbicularis*, *Asplenium javorkaeum*; Orthoptera: *Chorthippus eisentrauti* (Ramme, 1951), *Saga pedo* (Pallas, 1771) are likewise considered indigenous elements of the local fauna.

During the past 57 years, Mount Szársomlyó and other localities within the Villány Mountains have been repeatedly surveyed by numerous collectors. Despite these efforts, the species has not been observed again. The present author has also conducted regular field observations throughout September and October over the last four decades, without obtaining any evidence of its continued occurrence. To clarify the status of the record, the author contacted Z. Varga via email to request access to the voucher specimens, as a possible misidentification was considered. According to Varga, the relevant specimens could not be located in his collection. Based on these circumstances, it must be concluded that no verifiable material of *Triodia*

amasinus is currently known from Hungary. Consequently, pending the discovery of reliably documented specimens, the species should be excluded from the Hungarian Lepidoptera fauna. Nevertheless, the existence of a small, “latent” population in the southernmost mountainous region of Hungary cannot be entirely ruled out, as such a population might persist below the current detection threshold and thus remain unrecorded despite repeated surveys.

Psychidae

Whittleia undulella (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1837) (Figs 4–8)

Solenobia undulella Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1837: 86, figs. 39 a, b, c. Type locality: Hungary, Ofen (=Buda[pest]). The original type specimens were lost or severely damaged (see Treitschke Collection in HNHM, Budapest). A neotype is designated from near the original locality (see Csepel). Neotype, designated below; slide-mounted, deposited at HNHM: adult male; Hungary | Csepel (Ung.) | 7. IV. 1933 | A. Friedrich | coll. Gergely |

General Distribution. *W. undulella* displays a markedly disjunct distribution pattern within the Palearctic Region. Outside the Carpathian Basin, the species occurs only in isolated, highly localised populations. Confirmed records are restricted to Ukraine, Russia, and Kazakhstan, with a single unverified report from the Retezat Mountains (Romania).

Regional Distribution. In Hungary, occurrences are confined to two primary regions. Most records originate from the sandy landscapes of the Danube–Tisza Interfluvium, which constitutes the species' core distribution and principal habitat system. In contrast, only four records exist for Transdanubia (Mezőföld and the Buda Mountains). Although most known sites are located within protected national parks, the species remains largely overlooked in Hungarian conservation practice. Given that *W. undulella* was originally described from Hungary and the country supports the largest known European populations, intensified research and conservation efforts are warranted. The distributional dataset and interpretations presented here are based on the author's primary field observations and a previously published synthesis (Fazekas, 2015).

Biology and Habitat. The host plant remains officially unknown. However, based on the author's ecological observations, *Potentilla arenaria* Borkh., *P. thyrsoiflora* Hülsen in Zimm., and *P. leucopolitana* Müll. (Rosaceae) are considered the most probable candidates. Larvae overwinter, and adults emerge from early April to late June. Flight activity occurs primarily during daylight hours, particularly in the afternoon, at elevations between 80 and 300 m a.s.l. The species shows a pronounced preference for Pannonian sandy steppes and dune habitats. These endemic ecosystems, centred in Hungary, extend into neighbouring regions of Austria, Slovakia, Romania, Bulgaria, and Serbia. The vegetation is characterised by open sandy grasslands dominated by tussock-forming grasses, specifically *Festuca vaginata* and *Stipa borysthena*. Additionally, the species has been locally recorded in limestone hill habitats up to 300 m (e.g., Mt. Somlyó at Fót; Mt. Mátyás in Budapest), where it is considered rare.

New Observations (Villány Mountains). Previously, *W. undulella* was unrecorded from the hilly regions of Southern Transdanubia. In early April 2025, the author observed three specimens on Mt. Tenkes (Harkány). Subsequently, in mid-March 2026, Zsolt Kalotás documented nearly a dozen males on Mt. Szársomlyó (Nagyharsány) shortly before dusk, capturing several high-quality photographs. These findings establish *W. undulella* as a new faunal element of the Villány Mountains (cf. Fazekas, 2002).

Habitat Description and Plant Communities of Mt. Szársomlyó. The southern macro-slope of Mt. Szársomlyó (Villány Mountains, South Hungary) constitutes a unique biogeographic enclave characterised by a pronounced sub-Mediterranean climatic influence. Due to its high degree of isolation, steep limestone and Mesozoic dolomite gradients, and thin rendzina soil layers, the vegetation exhibits a complex mosaic structure. This is primarily classified under the *Inulo spiraeifoliae-Quercetum pubescentis* (sub-Mediterranean xerothermic karst shrub-forests) and *Chrysopogono-Festucetum dalmaticae* (rocky sward communities) phytosociological units.

Key Floral Elements and Taxonomic Composition. A high proportion of Illyrian and Balkanic floral elements defines the xerothermic vegetation. The canopy layer of the karst shrub-forest is dominated by *Quercus pubescens* Willd. and *Fraxinus ornus* L., forming a sparse, low-stature woodland that supports a species-rich herbaceous layer. The open rocky

Fig. 4. *Wittleia undulella* observation sites in Hungary (red dots by Fazekas 2015). Green dots in black frames indicate observations (2022-2026, see in text).

grasslands (*Festucetalia valesiaca*) are of outstanding conservation value, harbouring several glacial relicts and steno-endemic taxa. The most significant species is the Hungarian Crocus, *Colchicum hungaricum* Janka (Colchicaceae), which reaches its northernmost global distribution limit on this specific limestone ridge. Its early phenology (blooming from late January) is a direct consequence of the unique microclimate.

Synecological Characteristics. Vegetation dynamics are strictly governed by the "edaphic compensation" effect, where the southern aspect and limestone parent material mitigate the effects of higher latitude, creating a refugium for thermophilous species. This community serves as a critical habitat for various xerophilous invertebrates, aligning its botanical importance with the zoological significance of the Danube-Drava National Park (DDNP). Mt. Tenkes (408 m a.s.l.) Mt. Tenkes constitutes the westernmost prominent massif of the Villány Mountains in Southern Transdanubia. Situated within the Praeillyricum floristic district, the mountain serves as a significant ecological transition zone where sub-Mediterranean climatic influences intersect with continental deciduous forest biomes. In contrast to the sheer, xeric limestone surfaces of neighbouring Mt. Szársomlyó, Mt. Tenkes is characterised by more extensive forest cover and deeper brown forest soil profiles, supporting a structurally complex and closed vegetation matrix.

The vegetation of Mount Tenkes. The vegetation of Mount Tenkes is strictly categorised under the following primary syntaxonomic and community designations:

Inulo spiraeifoliae-Quercetum pubescentis (Sub-Mediterranean xerothermic karst shrub-forests): Dominating the steep, south-facing limestone gradients.

Asperulo taurinae-Carpinetum (Illyrian silver lime-hornbeam-oak forests): Representing the climax community on the northern slopes and in humid valley systems, distinguished by the presence of *Tilia tomentosa* Moench.

Aconito anthorae-Fraxinetum ornii: Xeromesophilous mixed forests occurring in mosaic patterns with shrubland fragments.

Potentillo-Quercetum pubescentis: Thermophilous oak forest fragments transitioning into closed woodland.

Festuco-Brometea (Sub-Mediterranean dry grasslands): Found primarily in secondary ha-

Figs 5–8. Wing patterns of male *Whittleia undulella* in the Villány Mountains (5–6); locations and habitats; Mt. Tenkes (7), rocky grassland on Szársomlyó Mountain (8). Photos: 1, 2, and 8 were taken by Zsolt Kalotás. See the text for further details.

bitats, abandoned vineyards, and forest edges, maintaining a high density of orchidaceous taxa.

Key Ecological Distinction of Mount Sársomlyó and Mount Tenkes. While both massifs belong to the Villány Mountains and share the same limestone basement, Sársomlyó acts as a xeric refugium for Balkanic and Mediterranean floral elements due to its bare rock surfaces. In contrast, Tenkes represents a mesic woodland ecosystem, in which the Sub-Mediterranean influence is expressed by the presence of Illyrian forest species such as Silver Lime (*Tilia tomentosa*) and evergreen shrubs.

Gelechiidae

Dirhinosisia cervinella (Eversmann, 1844) (Figs 9–10)

Lita cervinella Eversmann, 1844

Description. Wingspan 16–18 mm. Head, thorax and tegula yellowish to ochreous-brown. Labial palpus white, recurved; apex of the third segment variably mottled with brown scales. Antenna brown, annulated with white. Forewing ochreous-brown, with yellowish scales mottling the basal area; in worn specimens, the ground colour becomes more uniformly yellowish-brown. Two distinct white fasciae are present: the first oblique, extending from approximately one-quarter of the costa to one-half of the dorsum, terminating beyond the fold; the second nearly straight, running from three-quarters of the costa to about three-fifths of the dorsum. Several small white spots situated near the termen, sometimes absent or fused into a narrow streak. Fringe concolourous with the forewing, bearing indistinct lines. Hindwing brown to dark brown.

Figs 9–10. *Dirhinusia cervinella*, adult (9), habitat of in Mt. Tenkes (10). The natural vegetation has been degraded, and the *Robinia pseudoacacia* is spreading rapidly.

Male genitalia. Uncus basally broad, triangular, apically pointed. Tegumen broad. Gnathos absent. Valva of nearly uniform width throughout, distally rounded. Sacculus robust, exceeding half the length of the valva; sacculus process short, about one-third the length of the sacculus base. Saccus medium-sized, pointed. Aedeagus elongate, approximately as long as the entire genital capsule, markedly broadened basally and narrowing distally; vesica armed with numerous minute cornuti.

Female genitalia. Apophyses posteriores are about twice as long as segment VIII. Apophyses anteriores are shorter than segment VIII. Ostium bursae elongate, densely covered with fine spines, distally forming a plicate, rounded protrusion. The ductus bursae are extremely long. Colliculum simple. Bursa copulatrix oval; signum an oval, serrate plate bearing a long, pointed lobe.

Bionomics. Early developmental stages and life history remain unknown. Adults have been recorded in June–July. Specimens from Hungary were attracted to a petroleum lamp in a steppe habitat on Mt Sár-hegy (Mátra Mountains near Gyöngyös).

General Distribution. Recorded from Russia (Southern Ural, Lower Volga region), Ukraine (Lugansk region), Hungary, Bulgaria, Croatia (Dalmatia), and Turkey.

Regional Distribution. The first specimens in Hungary were observed by Buschmann on Sár Hill, located in northern Hungary at the foot of the Mátra Mountains near Lake Anna, on June 11, 1997. He observed additional specimens in 2001 and 2002 (Buschmann 2003). A total of 20 specimens have been found so far.

New record: Southern Hungary, Villány Mountains, Mt. Tenkes, June 28, 2025, 2 specimens collected by I. Fazekas. A detailed habitat description is provided in the species profile for *Whittleia undulella* (Fazekas, 2024). The linear distance between the Villány and Mátra Mountains is approximately 170–180 km. To the south, the nearest populations are located along the Dalmatian coast in Croatia, roughly 300–350 km away. These highly fragmented and isolated *D. cervinella* populations in Hungary appear critically threatened, despite their presence within protected natural areas. In the intervening regions, the potential for gene flow is effectively nonexistent.

Notes. To date, a single species of the genus *Dirhinusia* has been documented from Hungary, namely *Dirhinusia cervinella* (Eversmann, 1844). This taxon was previously misidentified by Buschmann (2000) as *Chionodes lugubrella* (Fabricius, 1794). Although Buschmann (2003) subsequently corrected this determination, no justification for the revision was provided. Szabóky (2001) presented a tabular comparison of these two morphologically similar species, noting that genitalia examinations had been conducted by Czech and Slovak specialists; however, the results of these examinations were not reported, and no genitalia illustrations were included in the publication.

According to Tokar & Gozmány (2004), *Dirhinosisia* is a poorly known and unrevised genus of Gelechiidae, established by Rebel (1905) based on the female holotype of *D. trifasciella* from Monastir, Bulgaria. Four valid Palearctic species are currently recognised: *D. unifasciella* (Rebel, 1929), *D. cervinella* (Eversmann, 1844), *D. nitidula* (Stainton, 1867) and *D. arnoldiella* (Rebel, 1905) distributed from southern Central and Eastern Europe through the Balkans and Asia Minor to the Middle East.

While Karsholt & Razowski (1996) treated *D. cervinella* and *D. trifasciella* as distinct, Tokar & Gozmány (2004) supported their synonymy. Specimens of *D. arnoldiella* collected in Greece were initially regarded as distinct based on minor differences in external morphology and male genitalia, but these are now considered intraspecific variation; the species is therefore newly recorded from Europe.

Members of *Dirhinosisia* are characterised by conspicuous forewing fasciae on a yellow-ochreous to reddish-brown ground colour and by distinctive genitalic traits, including a neck-like dorsal extension of the sacculus in males and an elongate ductus bursa in females.

Oecophoridae

Dasycera oliviella (Fabricius, 1794) (Figs 11–12)

Tinea oliviella Fabricius, 1794

Bionomy. The larva develops beneath the bark of senescent, dying deciduous and coniferous trees, and may also utilise lichens as an additional food source. Recorded host plants encompass a broad range of genera, including *Picea*, *Pinus*, *Prunus*, *Pyrus*, *Morus*, *Robinia*, *Ulmus*, *Betula*, *Corylus*, and *Castanea sativa*. Lives in various colline and montane hay meadows, acid grasslands and heaths, halophytic habitats, dry open grasslands, white oak scrub woodlands, thermophilous woodland fringes, semi-natural vegetation of abandoned vineyards and orchards, etc.

General Distribution. In Central Europe, the species is known primarily from scattered warm habitats in the region's southern parts. Verified records originate from Austria (Carinthia, North Tyrol, Styria, Burgenland), South Moravia, the southern and central regions of Slovakia, and Hungary. In Germany, the species has recently been detected near Regensburg, with older records available from additional localities. From Poland, only historical findings are known, all from the province of Dolnośląskie. Overall, the species is considered highly local and rare, though it may occasionally occur in higher numbers. Additional scattered records extend from southeastern England, across parts of central, southern, and northern Eu-

Figs 11–12. *Dasycera oliviella*, adult (11), habitat of in Mt. Tettye, Pécs (12); The site is an inactive limestone quarry characterised by a south-facing, successional area partially covered by scrub vegetation. A black pine forest in the upper part of the picture, with many dying trees. Partial description in the text.

rope, reaching Ukraine, the southern portion of European Russia, and Turkey (Tokar et al. 2005).

Regional Distribution. It is widespread throughout Hungary, but there have been few sightings anywhere. In Baranya County, it has been observed only in the botanical garden of the University of Pécs for more than 60 years; there have been no new sightings since then (Fazekas 2002).

New data. H-Pécs, 350 m, Mecsekoldal, Tettye, 31.v.2016, leg. I. Fazekas.

Habitat. The study site is an inactive limestone quarry characterised by a south-facing, successional area partially covered by scrub vegetation. To the north, the habitat transitions into karst scrub forests and anthropogenic stands of black pine (*Pinus nigra*).

Tortricidae

Cochylidia moguntiana (Rössler, 1864) (Figs 13–16)

Tortrix (*Conchylis*) *moguntiana* Rössler, 1864

Bionomy. Bivoltine; iv–vi, vii–ix. Larva monophagous in stems of *Artemisia campestris*. Lives in various colline and montane hay meadows, acid grasslands and heaths, Halophylic habitats, dry open grasslands, white oak scrub woodlands, thermophilous woodland fringes, semi-natural vegetation of abandoned vineyards and orchards, etc. (Fazekas 2024).

General Distribution. Transpalearctic species through southern Siberia and central Asia to western Europe.

Regional Distribution. Small populations are scattered in lowlands and hilly areas in Hungary.

New data. Nagyarsány, Szársomlyó, 26.iv.2000.leg. I. Fazekas.

Note. In Transdanubia, it was previously known only from the Bakony and Mecsek Mountains. A new species in the fauna of the Villány Mountains (see Fazekas 2002).

Figs 12–16. *Cochylidia moguntiana*: distribution in Hungary (13), habitat in Mt. Szársomlyó, south-facing dry rocky grassland and karst scrub forest complex (14), male genitalia, the aedeagus with many small cornutus (15), adult (16). In Hungary, the wingspan is 10–15 mm, and the pattern is variable. The specimen was disturbed and collected during the day.

Crambidae

Ecpyrrhorhoe diffusalis (Guenée, 1854) (Figs 17–19)

Botys diffusalis Guénée, 1854, Histoire naturelle des insectes 8, p. 340. Locus typicus: "France méridionale, environs de Nîmes et Montpellier".

Regional Distribution. Szent-Ivány and Uhrik-Mészáros (1942) published it from several localities outside the present Hungary: „Herkulesfürdő“ (in Romania: Baile Herculeane) and Zengg (in Croatia: Senj). Szabóky (1980) recorded firstly from Hungary: South Hungary, Villány Mountains, Nagyharsány, near the Croatian border.

Until 2007, our knowledge of the species *E. diffusalis* was as follows (Fazekas 2014). The known localities of *E. diffusalis* are situated at approximately 190 m a.s.l. (Villány Mountains, Szársomlyó), where the species typically inhabits calcareous, open rocky grasslands characterised by high diversity of endemic and relict vascular plants, including *Trigonella gladiata*, *Colchicum hungaricum*, *Medicago orbicularis*, *Orobanche nana*, and *Sempervivum tectorum*. The characteristic plant association of these habitats is the *Sedo sopianae*–*Festucetum dalmaticae* community developing on Triassic and Jurassic limestone substrates (Simon 1964). In addition to *E. diffusalis*, several other rare microlepidopteran species have been recorded from these sites, such as *Triodia amasinus* and *Jordanita fazekasi*. The isolated, relictual and xerothermophilous population of *E. diffusalis* occurring in southern Hungary is predominantly confined to this protected area designated within the Natura 2000 network. Despite its apparent rarity, the species is not listed in the Hungarian Red Data Book (Rakonczay 1989) and currently lacks formal legal protection. Based on its distribution pattern and ecological requirements, *E. diffusalis* is interpreted as a regressive postglacial relict element.

An unexpected record was obtained in 2007, when an automatic light trap operated at Gunarasfürdő, situated approximately 63 km north of the Villány Mountains, captured a specimen of *E. diffusalis* (Fazekas & Schreurs 2014). This finding is particularly noteworthy in light of the presence of the Mecsek Mountains, whose elongated massif rises to elevations exceeding 600 m and forms a substantial geographic barrier between the two localities. Despite intensive lepidopterological investigations in the Mecsek Mountains since the mid-nineteenth century, the occurrence of *E. diffusalis* had not been previously documented there.

The record was unexpected, not only because of the considerable distance involved, but also because of the pronounced ecological differences between the sites. In contrast to the characteristic habitat mosaic of the Villány Mountains – comprising dry limestone cliffs and karst scrub forests – the Gunarasfürdő locality is situated on the periphery of a resort area, in proximity to the floodplain of the Kapos River. The surrounding landscape is dominated by agricultural fields, wet meadows, and riparian tree stands.

New data from the Mecsek Mountains. This notable disjunction prompted targeted surveys within the intervening Mecsek Mountains, focusing on habitats that had previously been only sparsely sampled by lepidopterists. Fieldwork was concentrated on Mt. Tubes at an elevation of approximately 600 m, where an extensive limestone rocky grassland occurs, bordered by karst scrub vegetation. During daytime collecting in June 2025, the first specimen of *E. diffusalis* was successfully recorded from the mountain range.

The Tubes peak near Pécs is part of the West Mecsek Landscape Protection Area, the HUDD20030 "Mecsek" Special Area of Conservation (SAC; part of the European Union's Natura 2000 network), and the HUDD10007 "Mecsek" Special Protection Area (SPA) for birds. The habitat type is classified as H2 calcareous rocky steppes [Natura 2000: 6240] (*Serratulo radiatae*–*Brometum pannonicum* and *Artemisio saxatilis*–*Festucetum dalmaticae*).

Note. Between the Villány Mountains and the Mecsek Mountains, there are no documented habitat complexes suitable for the presence of *E. diffusalis* populations. To the north, extending toward the Kapos River (Gunarasfürdő), the landscape consists primarily of intensive agricultural land lacking viable habitats for the species. Due to the absence of ecological "stepping stones" between these three fragmented populations, gene flow is effectively precluded; consequently, the species is considered critically endangered within Hungary.

Figs 17–18.

Location of *Ecpyrrhorhoe diffusalis* in Kis-Tubes (17); the pattern of the adult wing (18).

A detailed description of the habitat can be found in the text.

Fig. 19. A vegetation map of the Tubes-Misina-Tettye mountain range (Mecsek Mountains), modified based on Horvát (1972). The observation site of *Ecpyrrhorhoe diffusalis* (f= XX) on the rocky, grassy mountain slope (*Serratulo radiatae-Brometum pannonici et Artemisio saxatilis-Festucetum dalmaticae*). All around it is a forest of downy oaks (d: *Tamo-Quercetum virginialae*).

Additions to the vegetation map shown in Figure 19 according to Horvát 1972:

Potentillo micranthae-Quercetum daleshampii (a)

Asperulo taurinae-Carpinetum (b)

Helleboro odoro-Fagetum (c)

Inulo spiraeifoliae-Quercetum pubescentis (e)

Luzulo forsteri-Quercetum petraeae (g)

Cultura Pini (h)

Horvát (1972) conducted coenological and mapping studies during the 1950s and 1960s. Over the past few decades, the boundaries of plant communities have changed substantially. The extent of rocky grasslands has declined markedly, with many areas becoming overgrown by shrubs. The situation is further exacerbated by the impacts of rapidly expanding tourism. This process is not conducive to the persistence of the isolated population of *E. diffusalis*.

Lycaenidae

Polyommatus amandus (Schneider, 1792) (Figs 20–22)

Papilio amandus Schneider, 1792, Neuestes Magazin für die Liebhaber der Entomologie 1:428

Syn.: *Papilio icarius* Esper, 1793

Polyommatus amandus is a legally protected butterfly species in Hungary and is included in the national Red Book. Globally, it is currently classified as Least Concern (LC) on the IUCN Red List, a category assigned to taxa that do not meet the quantitative criteria for threatened categories such as Near Threatened, Vulnerable, Endangered or Critically Endangered, and are generally considered to possess relatively large or stable populations.

In Hungary, however, the conservation situation of *P. amandus* appears to be markedly less favourable. No stable populations are presently known, and the species has disappeared from numerous formerly occupied localities, with several sites lacking confirmed records for many decades. Based on historical data and field observations accumulated since the late nineteenth century, the species shows a pronounced declining trend within the country. This interpretation is consistent with recent national assessments of threatened butterfly species, in which *P. amandus* was assigned Near Threatened (NT) status (Gergely & Hudák 2021).

Earlier studies (Fazekas 2006, 2026) also addressed the historical occurrence of *P. amandus* in the Mecsek Mountains. Referring to Balogh (1978; under the name *icarius*), a specimen collected near Pécs in June 1891 (leg. Viertel) was reported; however, this material is no longer available for verification. During the subsequent century, no confirmed records have been obtained from the Mecsek region, and the species should therefore be regarded as regionally extinct or, at a minimum, strongly regressing. This absence is notable because several extensive areas within the mountains still provide apparently suitable habitat conditions, including sites designated within the Natura 2000 network.

Following the publication of the aforementioned descriptions (Fazekas 2026), Kálmán Szeőke (pers. comm in e-mail) reported that he had collected two specimens of *P. amandus* in 2013 near the village of Cserkút, located in the western foothills of the Mecsek Mountains. He also sent me a photo identifying the specimens. This proved that, after nearly 140 years of “hiding,” there is indeed a breeding population of *P. amandus* in Hungary’s southernmost mountain range. Thus, the species has not gone extinct and has not disappeared from this geographical area. Below, I present the population’s habitat, which is unique in the country and is not known to exist anywhere else in Hungary:

Vegetation Characteristics of the Cserkút Region. Cserkút and its immediate vicinity, particularly the southern slopes of the towering Jakab Mount, represent one of the most ecologically unique areas of the Mecsek Mountains. In this region, the vegetation is primarily determined by red sandstone (the Jakab Mount Sandstone Formation) and the resulting acidic soils, rather than the limestone characteristic of the wider range.

The vegetation of the Cserkút landscape is categorised by the following primary types and characteristics:

1. **Acidophilous Forest Communities.** While the majority of the Mecsek Mountains is characterized by calciphilous (lime-loving) flora, the acidic bedrock above Cserkút has facilitated the development of rare acidophilous (lime-avoiding) communities.

Genisto tinctoriae-Quercetum petraeae submediterraneum: This is one of the rarest communities in the mountain range, thriving specifically on the weathered debris of red sandstone. The undergrowth frequently features the spiny butcher 's-broom (*Ruscus aculeatus*), a diagnostic species of sub-Mediterranean influence. Acidophilous Beech Forests: These occur in the cooler microclimates and deeper valleys of Jakab Hill, where soil pH levels remain low. Stunted Oak Woodlands: On the rocky ridges near the Babás-szerkövek formation, characterised by shallow topsoil, the trees (primarily sessile oaks) remain stunted with twisted trunks due to extreme environmental stressors.

2. **Rocky Grasslands and Scrub Forests (Southern Slopes).** The steep slopes between the village and Jakab Hill are dominated by southern, Mediterranean-like exposure. Acidophilous Rocky Grasslands: Open communities inhabit the sandstone outcrops (e.g., around the Babás-szerkövek). Notable species include the small pasque flower (*Pulsatilla nigricans*) and,

Figs 20–21.

Diagnostic characteristic of *Polyommatus amandus*: (20) top view, (21) underside (A collecting organized by the Hungarian Society for Biodiversity Research (photo: K. Szeőke)

Fig. 22.

The habitat of *Polyommatus amandus* in the Cserkút area, with the Mecsek mountain range in the distance. A detailed description can be found in the text. The photo was taken by Cs. Kutasi.

during the spring, the grape hyacinth (*Muscari botryoides*).

Dry Grasslands and Shrublands: The areas surrounding former uranium mining sites and the hills at the village periphery form a mosaic landscape where hawthorn and blackthorn co-exist with species-rich wildflower meadows.

It was within this vegetation complex that a fragment of the only known population of *P. amandus* was discovered, a finding that calls for further, more thorough niche studies that are also important from a faunal history perspective.

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Magyar nyelvű összefoglaló / Summary in Hungarian

Új megfigyelések és jegyzetek a Baranya megyei lepkékről (Lepidoptera)

Fazekas Imre

A tanulmány Baranya megye lepkefaunájának (Lepidoptera) új és jelentős faunisztikai adatait mutatja be. A szerző az 1970-es évektől folytatott kutatásaira építve több mint 2000 faj előfordulását dokumentálta, köztük ritka vagy korábban csak irodalmi adatokból ismert taxonokat. A vizsgálat célja egyes fajok hazai státuszának kritikai felülvizsgálata, valamint új előfordulási adatok közlése a biogeográfiaileg kiemelt jelentőségű dél-dunántúli térségből.

Vizsgálati terület: Baranya megye Magyarország legdélibb régiója, ahol a szubmediterrán klímahatás és a balkáni faunisztikai kapcsolatok különösen erősek. A Villányi-hegység és a Mecsek változatos élőhelyei – xerotherm mészkősziklagyepek, karsztbokorerdők, savanyú talajú erdők és más mozaikos vegetációtípusok – kulcsszerepet játszanak a lepkefajok fennmaradásában és terjedésében

Anyag és módszer: A közlemény a szerző több évtizedes terepi megfigyeléseire, gyűjtéseire, valamint irodalmi és múzeumi adatokra épül. A fajok előfordulását vegetációtani és élőhely-típológiai rendszerben értelmezi, hangsúlyozva az „ökológiai lépcsőkövek” szerepét a populációk fennmaradásában és genetikai kapcsolatában.

Főbb eredmények:

1. Új vagy jelentős faunisztikai adatok

***Whittleia undulella*:** első bizonyított előfordulás a Villányi-hegységben; a faj hazai természetvédelmi jelentősége nagyobb a korábban feltételezetténél.

***Dirhinosisa cervinella*:** új lelőhely a Tenkes-hegyen; a magyarországi populációk erősen izoláltak és veszélyeztetettek. Új faj a Dunántúlon.

***Cochylidia moguntiana*:** új adat a Szársomlyóról; a faj a Villányi-hegység faunájának új eleme.

***Epyrrhorhoe diffusalis*:** a Mecsekben is kimutatott, ami korábban feltételezett elterjedési diszkontinuitást módosít; reliktumjellegű, kritikusan veszélyeztetett populációk.

***Dasycera oliviella*:** ritka faj, Baranyában hosszú ideig nem volt friss adata; új megfigyelés Pécs környékéről.

2. Fajstátusz-revizíó

***Triodia amasinus*:** a korábbi (1969-es) magyarországi adat nem igazolható, ezért a faj jelenleg kizárandó a hazai faunából, bár egy rejtett reliktumpopuláció lehetősége nem zárható ki.

3. Természetvédelmi megállapítások

***Polyommatus amandus*:** Magyarországon erősen visszaszorult, de a Mecsek déli részén egy kis, egyedi élőhelyhez kötött szaporodó populáció fennmaradását sikerült igazolni.

Több vizsgált faj esetében a populációk fragmentáltak, genetikai kapcsolat nélküliek, ami növeli kipusztulási kockázatukat.

Következtetések: A dél-dunántúli hegységek különleges mikroklímája és vegetációmozaikja refúgiumként működik számos balkáni és mediterrán eredetű lepkefaj számára. A tanulmány hangsúlyozza, hogy a fajok elterjedésének értelmezése csak élőhely- és vegetációalapú megközelítéssel lehet megalapozott. Az új adatok fontosak a hazai lepkefauna revíziója és a természetvédelmi prioritások kijelölése szempontjából.

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